

Table 1: Interview Codebook (Merged).

Category	Codes	Definition or example
Participant Background	Work background	Profession of participants
	Education background	Education of participants
	UPI usage frequency	No: of transactions in a day
	UPI usage duration	No: of months/years of usage
	Mobile OS	Android or iOS
	Devices	Device types- mobile, tab or laptop/PC
	UPI apps	Apps they used so far
	Knowledge gap	Participant knowledge gap with settings and features
Initial Signup & Source	Reason of UPI usage	Like government mandates, pandemic, cashless movements, etc
	Source of Info	Family, friends, ads, promos, etc
	Source of learning	Google, friends, family, documents, self-learned, etc
Usage Motivations	Reason for using	Rewards, cashback, ease of use
	Usage reasons of UPI	Fast, secure, cashless, easy, avoid banks, ATMs, cash
Transaction Types	Day-to-day transactions	Food, online shopping, transportation, sending to family, friends
	Recurring/auto-debit	Entertainment subscriptions, maintaining a minimum balance, bill reminders
	Types of transactions	Ticket bookings, online shopping, food ordering, paying bills, sending to family, friends
	Receiving- success verification	Check the history, account balance, confirmation from the receiver, notification from banks, UPI
Transaction Verification	Sending- success verification	Check account balance, history, notifications from banks, UPI, confirmation from receiver
	Sending- failure verification	Check history, notifications
	Source of settings information	Google search, FAQs, social media, official guidance from UPI, self-learned
Safety Measures Sources	UPI settings for safety	2-factor, biometric authentications, PIN safety
	Source of UPI safety measures	Own intuition, social media, friends, family, information from banks, UPI providers

Category	Codes	Definition or example
	Security measures by users	Avoid sharing sensitive details- OTP, PIN, careful in public, double-check receiver details, etc
Rationale	Rationale provided	Whether participants explained their choices of using or not using security settings, explanations for concerns, and advice they receive
	No Rationale	When participants mentioned a security choice they made without providing further explanation.
Guidance & Awareness	Handling UPI issues	Contact official help desk, discuss with family, friends, report suspicion
	Guidance from UPI provider/banks	Don't share sensitive details with officials, follow guidelines, avoid unknown calls, emails, texts, links
	Users preferred awareness platforms	Official websites, social media, official contacts from banks, UPI providers
	Measures to increase awareness	Increase campaigns, prioritize targeted promotions, educate over social media, other sources
	Miscellaneous statements	Few supporting statements made by participants
Concerns & Challenges	Concerns	Risks with PIN-less transactions, the authenticity of QR codes, payment links, etc
	Challenges	Server glitches, internet issues, scanner problems, transaction failures, cybercrime cases
	Watchful scenarios	Paying with links, QR codes, high volume transactions, unknown merchants
	Concerns with UPI settings	Avoid auto-pay options, forgetting setting changes, etc
	Technical challenges	Issues with QR, lack of KYC, server problems, etc
	App-specific challenges	Bank server downtimes, ease of use, lot of options, etc
Scams & Frauds Details	Heard/read experiences	Sharing OTP on call, transactions with links, other experiences
	Experienced scams/frauds with UPI	Its Yes or No, whether participants experienced scams/frauds
	Personal experiences	Clicking on unknown links, posting on the online marketplace, job offers, cashback, etc
	Major source of scams	Online marketplace, calls, advertisements, sharing OTP, PIN, etc
	Impact of scams, frauds	Ignore unknown calls, links, block suspicious contacts, don't share OTP, PIN, QR codes, verify receiver details

Category	Codes	Definition or example
Handling Lost/Repair Devices	Safety measures before mobile repair	Uninstall banking apps, hiding apps, removing SIM cards, taking backups, switching off mobile, removing battery, etc.
	Concerns before mobile repair	Repair technicians knowledge for hacking device etc
	Safety measures after losing phone	Block account, changing PIN online, blocking all apps, lodging police complaint, etc
	Concerns after losing phone	Trusting reboot process, confidence on locks, losing contacts
	Lost mobile	Whether participant lost mobile or not, its Yes or No
	Given mobile for repair	Whether participant gave mobile for repair or not, its Yes or No